

STUDY THE ANTIBIOTIC THERAPY AND ITS RECOVERY TIME IN PATIENTS SUFFERING WITH BRONCHOPNEUMONIA OF AGE GROUP 5 MONTHS TO 5 YEARS IN PEDIATRICS I.C.U/WARD IN A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL

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Received: May 05, 2025

Accepted: Jun 06, 2025

Published: Jun 07, 2025

Abstract

Background: Bronchopneumonia is one of the leading causes of morbidity and mortality in children under five years of age, particularly in developing countries. Timely initiation of effective antibiotic therapy plays a crucial role in reducing complications and shortening recovery time.

Objective: This study aims to evaluate the patterns of antibiotic therapy and its impact on the recovery time in pediatric patients aged 5 months to 5 years diagnosed with bronchopneumonia and admitted to the Pediatric I.C.U. or ward of a tertiary care hospital.

Methods: A prospective observational study was conducted involving children aged 5 months to 5 years diagnosed with bronchopneumonia. Data collected included demographic information, clinical symptoms, type and duration of antibiotic therapy, length of hospital stay, and time to clinical recovery. Patients were monitored daily for clinical improvement, and data were analyzed to assess correlations between antibiotic regimens and recovery outcomes.

Results: The majority of patients responded favorably to first-line antibiotic therapy Amoxicillin, Azithromycin, Ceftriaxone, Amoxiclav etc with a mean recovery time of 1-4 days for single antibiotic. Delays in initiating appropriate antibiotics or resistance to initial therapy were associated with prolonged hospital stays. Factors such as nutritional status the presence of comorbidities also influenced recovery time.

Conclusion: Early and appropriate antibiotic therapy significantly reduces the recovery time in children suffering from bronchopneumonia. Regular monitoring and adherence to clinical guidelines are essential to ensure better outcomes in pediatric respiratory infections.

Keywords:

Bronchopneumonia, Pediatric ICU, Antibiotic therapy, Recovery time, Children under five, Respiratory infection, Tertiary care hospital, Antibiotic resistance.

INTRODUCTION

Pediatrics is defined as a branch of medicine dealing with development, care and disease of infants, children and adolescents. The most common diseases include Pneumonia, Anemia, Asthma, jaundice, Epilepsies.

Bronchopneumonia or Bronchogenic pneumonia is the acute inflammation of the walls of the bronchioles. It is one of two types of bacterial pneumonia as classified by gross anatomic distribution of consolidation, the other being lobar pneumonia. ^[1]

Bronchopneumonia or lobular pneumonia is a type of pneumonia that causes inflammation in the bronchi. These are the air passages that feed air into the lungs. ^[2] Bronchopneumonia is precipitated by inhalation (or rarely hematogenous spread) of a causative organism. This results in peribronchiolar inflammation, which can spread through the pores of Kohn to create consolidation throughout an entire secondary pulmonary lobule. ^[3]

EPIDEMIOLOGY:

Globally, pneumonia is a serious public health concern and a major cause of mortality and morbidity ^[4]. It is a common illness affecting approximately 450 million people a year and occurring in all parts of the world. ^[5] It is a major cause of death among all age groups, resulting in 1.4 million deaths in 2010 (7% of the world's yearly total). In 2014, the eighth cause of mortality in the United States reported by the National Centre for Health Statistics was influenza and pneumonia together ^[6]. In children, pneumonia is the single largest infectious cause of death worldwide. In 2015, pneumonia killed 920,136 children under the age of 5, accounting for 15% of all deaths of children less than five years old ^[7]. Globally, *Streptococcus pneumoniae* (pneumococcus) is the most common pathogen causing community-acquired pneumonia. Pneumococcus was considered one of the 9 bacteria of international concern in the recent worldwide report on global antibiotic resistance published by the World Health Organization (WHO) in 2014 ^[8]. Several studies on the microbial etiology of pneumonia have been published in recent years. Some of them showed that microbial causes of pneumonia differ according to the severity of the disease at clinical presentation. ^[9] A Spanish study regarding the relationship between microbial etiology of pneumonia and severity concluded that

pneumococcus is the most frequent pathogen in all sites of care. The second most frequent group of pathogens was intracellular microorganisms, followed by polymicrobial cases.^[10]

CLASSIFICATION:

Pneumonia can be classified in several ways, most commonly by where it was acquired (hospital versus community), but may also by the area of lung affected or by the causative organism.^[11] There is also a combined clinical classification, which combines factors such as age, risk factors for certain microorganisms, the presence of underlying lung disease or systemic disease, and whether the person has recently been hospitalized.

Pneumonia Classification

Classification

1. Etiology: most important because it serves as a *guide for treatment*
 - Bacteria, chlamydia, mycoplasmas, rickettsiae, viruses, fungi
2. Anatomic distribution of the inflammatory process—describes *what part of the lung* is involved
 - Lobar: *entire* lung (bacteria, neutrophil infiltration)
 - Bronchopneumonia (bacteria, neutrophil infiltration): *parts* of one or more lobes adjacent to the bronchi – bronchopulmonary segments

BASED ON ETIOLOGY:

Traditionally, clinicians have classified pneumonia by clinical characteristics, dividing them into "acute" (less than three weeks duration) and "chronic" pneumonia. This is useful because chronic pneumonias tend to be either non-infectious, or mycobacterial, fungal, or mixed bacterial infections caused by airway obstruction. Acute pneumonia are further divided into classic bacterial bronchopneumonia (such as *Streptococcus pneumoniae*), atypical pneumonia (such as the interstitial pneumonitis of *Mycoplasma pneumoniae* or *Chlamydia pneumoniae*) and aspiration pneumonia syndromes^[12]. Chronic pneumonias, on the other hand, mainly include those of *Nocardia*, *Actinomyces* and *Blastomyces* and *Dermatitis* well as the granulomatous pneumonias (*Mycobacterium tuberculosis* and atypical mycobacteria, *Histoplasma capsulatum*)^[13]

BASED ON ANATOMICAL DISTRIBUTION:

1. Lobar pneumonia is an infection that only involves a single lobe, or section, of a lung. Lobar pneumonia is often due to *Streptococcus pneumoniae* (though *Klebsiella pneumoniae* is also possible.)^[14]
2. Multi-lobe pneumonia involves more than one lobe, and it often causes a more severe illness.
3. Bronchopneumonia affects the lungs in patches around the tubes (bronchi or bronchioles).
4. Interstitial pneumonia involves the areas in between the alveoli, and it may be called "interstitial pneumonitis." It is more likely to be caused by viruses or by atypical bacteria.^[12]

ETIOLOGY:

Lower respiratory tract infections are a common cause of morbidity among children. Among these infections, pneumonia is the most serious illness and can be difficult to diagnose. The etiology of pneumonia is still partly unknown, primarily because of the difficulty in obtaining adequate samples and lack of reliable diagnostic methods.

Streptococcus pneumoniae is recognized as an important cause of pediatric pneumonia regardless of age in both the inpatient and outpatient setting. In developed countries *S. pneumoniae* probably accounts for 25 to 30% of cases of pediatric community-acquired pneumonia. Viruses (mostly

respiratory syncytial virus) are responsible for approximately 20% of cases, and Chlamydia pneumonia and Mycoplasma pneumonia occur commonly in older children.^[15]

COMMUNITY-ACQUIRED PNEUMONIA (CAP):

Infants can acquire lung infections before birth by breathing infected amniotic fluid or through a blood-borne infection that crossed the placenta. Infants can also inhale contaminated fluid from the vagina at birth. The most prevalent pathogen causing CAP in newborns is *Streptococcus agalactiae*, also known as group-B streptococcus (GBS). GBS causes more than half of CAP in the first week after birth.^[16] Other bacterial causes of neonatal CAP include *Listeria monocytogenes* and a variety of mycobacteria. CAP-causing viruses may also be transferred from mother to child; herpes simplex virus (the most common) is life-threatening, and adenoviral, mumps, and enterovirus can also cause pneumonia. Another cause of CAP in this group is *Chlamydia trachomatis*, acquired at birth but not causing pneumonia until two to four weeks later; it usually presents with no fever and a characteristic, staccato cough.

CAP in older infants reflects increased exposure to microorganisms, with common bacterial causes including *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Moraxella catarrhalis*, and *Staphylococcus aureus*. Maternally-derived syphilis is also a cause of CAP in this age group. Viruses include human respiratory syncytial virus (RSV), human metapneumovirus, adenovirus, human Para influenza viruses, influenza, and rhinovirus, and RSV is a common source of illness and hospitalization in infants.^[17]

HOSPITAL-ACQUIRED PNEUMONIA:

It is a condition in patients who can come from the community, but have frequent contact with the healthcare environment. Historically, the etiology and prognosis of nursing home pneumonia appeared to differ from other types of community acquired pneumonia, with studies reporting a worse prognosis and higher incidence of multi-drug resistant organisms as etiology agents. The definition criteria which has been used are the same as the ones that has been previously used to identify bloodstream healthcare-associated infections.^[18]

LOBAR PNEUMONIA:

It is a form of pneumonia characterized by inflammatory exudates within the intra-alveolar space resulting in consolidation that affects a large and continuous area of the lobe of a lung.^[19]

The most common organisms that cause lobar pneumonia are *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, also called pneumococcus, *Haemophilus influenzae*, and *Moraxella catarrhalis*. *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, the tubercle bacillus, may also cause lobar pneumonia if pulmonary tuberculosis is not treated promptly. Other organisms that cause lobar pneumonia are *Legionella pneumophila* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*.^[20]

MULTILOBAR PNEUMONIA:

Multilobar pneumonia (MLP) may have poorer outcomes and is a constituent of some prognostic indices.^[21] Multilobar pneumonia involves more than one lobe, and it often causes a more severe illness.^[12]

BRONCHOPNEUMONIA:

Many cases of bronchopneumonia are caused by bacteria. Outside the body, the bacteria are contagious and can spread between people nearby through sneezes and coughs. A person becomes infected by breathing in the bacteria.

Common bacterial causes of bronchopneumonia include:

- *Staphylococcus aureus*
- *Haemophilus influenzae*
- *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*
- *Escherichia coli*
- *Klebsiella pneumoniae*
- *Proteus species*^[21]

INTERSTITIAL PNEUMONIA:

Bacteria, viruses, or fungi may infect the interstitium of the lung. A bacterium called *Mycoplasma pneumoniae* is the most common cause.^[22] Interstitial pneumonia involves the areas in between the alveoli, and it may be called "interstitial pneumonitis." It is more likely to be caused by viruses or by atypical bacteria.^[12]

MANAGEMENT:

Antibacterial therapy is the mainstay of successful treatment of bacterial bronchopneumonia. There is a high level of probability that gram-negative aerobes are involved, then the selection of an antibacterial agent, with potent activity against such organisms, such as fluoroquinolone. Using the guidelines, the antibacterial appropriate for treating bacterial bronchopneumonia include potentiated sulphonamides, cephalosporins, fluoroquinolones, clindamycin, and metronidazole. Antibiotic therapy should be continued until 2-3 weeks after resolution of clinical signs and in some instances should be administered for up to 8 weeks. Initially, administration of antibacterial agents is preferably by the intravenous route. Subsequent maintenance therapy is given orally.

The other main consideration in the effective treatment of bronchopneumonia cases is adequate supportive care. This includes tending to the patient's dietary and fluid needs and providing supplemental oxygen. Intravenous fluid therapy is required to maintain proper hydration, as the patient is likely to be anorexic, but also as there will be fluid loss from the airway as a consequence of increased respiratory effort. The use of physiotherapy will be beneficial.^[23]

PEDIATRIC PNEUMONIA CLINICAL PRACTICE GUIDELINE:

These guidelines are provided to assist physicians and other clinicians in making decisions regarding the care of their patients. These are intended to assist clinicians in treating community-acquired pneumonia in otherwise healthy infants and children older than 3 months of age. These guidelines do not pertain to infants \leq 3 months of age, immune-compromised children, children with chronic lung disease (ex: cystic fibrosis), or ventilator-dependent children.

INITIAL PRESENTATION:

- Fever (temperature ≥ 38.0 C or 100.4 F)
- Cough
- Abnormal lung sounds (wheezing)
- Variable degrees of respiratory distress (tachypnoea, dyspnoea, retractions, grunting, nasal flaring, apnoea, altered mental status)

RISK FACTORS:

- Age < 5 years
- Male
- Prematurity
- Malnutrition

CONDITIONS THAT FAVOR IN-PATIENT MANAGEMENT:

- Respiratory distress (tachypnea, dyspnoea, retractions, grunting, nasal flaring, apnoea, altered mental status)
- Sustained SpO₂ < 90%
- < 3 months of age with suspected bacterial pneumonia

DIAGNOSTIC TESTING ROUTINELY RECOMMENDED:

- Pulse oximetry should be performed in all children with pneumonia and suspected hypoxemia. The presence of hypoxemia should guide decisions regarding site of care and further diagnostic testing.

NOT ROUTINELY RECOMMENDED:

- Chest x-ray is not necessary to confirm pneumonia in patients in the outpatient setting. Chest x-ray is a consideration for patients with a non-specific exam but persistent clinical symptoms consistent with pneumonia.
- Blood cultures are not routinely recommended for non-toxic, fully immunized children.

DRUG THERAPY:

- Amoxicillin should be used as first-line therapy for previously healthy, appropriately immunized infants and preschool children with mild to moderate pneumonia suspected to be of bacterial origin. Amoxicillin provides appropriate coverage for *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, the most prominent invasive bacterial pathogen.
- Macrolide antibiotics should be prescribed for the treatment of children (primarily school-aged children and adolescents) with findings compatible with pneumonia caused by atypical pathogens.

RESPONSE TO TREATMENT:

- a) Children receiving adequate therapy should demonstrate clinical signs of improvement within 48–72 hours. If repeat laboratory testing is done, ideally, there will be improvement from baseline labs. However, initial and repeat lab testing is not necessary, clinical improvement should be the determination of adequate therapy.
- b) For children who show no improvement in fever or clinical symptoms within 48-72 hours after diagnosis and initiation of antimicrobial therapy, consideration of further investigation or adjustment of antibiotic coverage should be performed.
- c) Clinical deterioration at any time should receive a higher level of care.

PATIENT EDUCATION:

Consult a physician, if your child shows any of the following warning signs that the pneumonia is getting worse.

- Fever lasting more than 3 days after starting antibiotics
- Increasing breathing difficulties
- Signs of dehydration, not drinking, repeated vomiting, and decreased urination.
- Evidence of an infection elsewhere in the body: red swollen joints, bone pain, severe headache, stiff neck, vomiting, or other new signs or symptoms.
- Skin around mouth or fingers looks blue or dusky.^[24-32]

MONITORING FOR ANTIBIOTIC DRUG THERAPY:

The following tests may be carried out as necessary:

Blood, urine, and cerebrospinal fluid cultures, a complete blood count with differential; and a chest radiograph should be obtained.

ALGORITHM FOR CHOICE OF ANTIBIOTIC THERAPY FOR PATIENTS WITH PNEUMONIA:

ABBREVIATIONS:

US, Ultrasound; CT, Computed Tomography; VATS, Video-Assisted Thoracoscopic Surgery; IR Drainage, Interventional Radiology Drainage; IV, Intravenous.

THIS TABLE SHOWS DETAILS REGARDING DRUG CLASS AND MECHANISM OF ACTION OF VARIOUS ANTIBIOTICS.

Doses and important side effects of commonly used antibiotics:

ANTIBIOTICS	DOSAGE RANGE	IMPORTANT SIDE EFFECTS	DRUG CLASS	MECHANISM OF ACTION
Amoxicillin	250 mg	Severe rash, seizures, chest pain, swelling of the face.	Aminopenicillins	Amoxicillin is similar to penicillin in its bactericidal action against susceptible bacteria during the stage of active multiplication. It acts through the inhibition of cell wall biosynthesis that leads to the death of the bacteria.
Azithromycin	500 mg for 1st dose, 250 mg for subsequent doses	Diarrhea, vomiting, abdominal pain.	Macrolide	It prevents bacteria from growing by interfering with their protein synthesis. It binds to the 50S subunit of the bacterial ribosome, thus inhibiting the translation of mRNA.
Ceftriaxone	50-100 mg/kg/day IM/IV divided q12-24h	Injection site reactions (swelling, redness, pain, a hard lump, or soreness), loss of appetite, headache, dizziness.	Third generation cephalosporin	Ceftriaxone selectively and irreversibly inhibits bacterial cell wall synthesis by binding to transpeptidases, also called transamidases, which are penicillin-binding proteins (PBPs) that catalyze the cross-linking of the peptidoglycan polymers forming the bacterial cell wall.

Amoxiclav	500mg	Skin rash or itching, White patches in your mouth or throat, Diarrhea.	Beta-lactamase inhibitor	Amoxicillin binds to penicillin-binding proteins within the bacterial cell wall and inhibits bacterial cell wall synthesis. Clavulanic acid is a β -lactam, structurally related to penicillin, that may inactivate certain β -lactamase enzymes.
Cefuroxime	50-100 mg/kg/day IM/IV divided q6- 8h	Nausea, vomiting, and diarrhea, Diaper rash, Kidney problems.	Second generation cephalosporin	Cefuroxime is a bactericidal agent that acts by inhibiting bacterial cell wall synthesis. It has activity in the presence of some β -lactamases, both penicillinases and cephalosporinases, of gram- negative and gram-positive bacteria.
Cefazolin	25mg/kg	Allergic reactions, Confusion, Diarrhea, Drowsiness, Eosinophilia.	First generation cephalosporin	Cephalosporins exert bactericidal activity by interfering with the later stages of bacterial cell wall synthesis through inactivation of one or more penicillin- binding proteins and inhibiting cross-linking of the peptidoglycan structure
Piptaz	4.5 g IV q6 h	Injection site reactions like. Swelling, redness, pain, soreness or irritation, Dizziness.	Beta-lactamase inhibitor	Tazobactam inhibits beta- lactamase and prevents the destruction of piperacillin. Therefore, Tazobactam is given with piperacillin to enhance the activity of piperacillin in eradicating

				bacterial infections. Piperacillin kills bacteria by inhibiting the synthesis of bacterial cell walls.
Amikacin	20g/kg/day IV	Hearing loss, or a roaring sound in your ears, Severe or ongoing dizziness, Kidney problems or no urinating, painful or difficult urination, swelling in your feet or ankles, feeling tired or short of breath.	Amino glycoside	Amikacin irreversibly binds to 16S rRNA and the RNA-binding S12 protein of the 30S subunit of the prokaryotic ribosome and inhibits protein synthesis by changing the ribosome's shape so that it cannot read the mRNA codons correctly. It also interferes with the region that interacts with the wobble base of the tRNA anticodon. It works in a concentration-dependent manner and has better action in an alkaline environment.
Gentamycin	10-12 mg/kg IV q24h	Nausea, vomiting, stomach upset, loss of appetite.	Amino glycoside	Gentamycin is a bactericidal antibiotic that works by irreversibly binding the 30S subunit of the bacterial ribosome, interrupting protein synthesis. This mechanism of action is similar to other aminoglycosides.
Cefotaxime	150-300 mg/kg/day IM/IV divided q6-8h	Severe stomach pain, and diarrhea that is watery or bloody.	Third generation cephalosporins	Cefotaxime sodium is a bactericidal agent that acts by inhibition of bacterial cell wall synthesis. Cefotaxime has acti

				vity in the presence of some beta-lactamases, both penicillinases and cephalosporinases, of Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria.
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ABBREVIATIONS: IV, Intravenous; IM, Intramuscular.

METHODOLOGY

The detailed illustration of this study was done by categorizing the methodology into five parts. The first part deals with study design. The second part includes ethical considerations. Third part consists of sampling technique, sample size determination. Fourth part includes participants. Final part consists of data collection and analysis.

Study Site and Study Design

The present study was carried out in the Department of Pediatrics, government general hospital, Kakinada for a duration 6 months. Our present study requires a prior hypothesis, data related to Antibiotic therapy and its recovery time in patients suffering from bronchopneumonia, follow-up required and samples of age groups 5 months to 5 years old are involved in this study. The above-mentioned study the characteristic are closely related to characteristic features of prospective study. So we have chosen the prospective study as our study design.

Ethical Consideration

Preceding the study, approval for the study was obtained from the pediatric Department, Government General Hospital, Kakinada.

Sampling Technique:

Based on the nature and aim of the study, a purposive sampling technique which involved using a predefined group of study subjects was used. This sampling technique would enable to obtain specific and relevant information about group of pediatric population with bronchopneumonia

and antibiotic therapy. The selection process can be described as purposive, judgmental based on strict selection criteria for the participants.

Sample Size: The sample size n and margin of error E are given by

$$X = Z_{(C/100)}^2 (100-r)$$

$$n = \frac{N \times X}{(N-1) E^2 + X}$$

$$E = \text{Sqrt} \left[\frac{(N-n) \times X}{n (N-1)} \right]$$

Where N is the population size $N = 100$,

r is the fraction of responses that you are interested in $r = 50\%$

$Z_{(C/100)}$ is the critical value for the confidence level c , $Z_{(C/100)} = 95\%$

By applying the above formula the sample size obtained is 80.

Participants:

The study was conducted at the government general hospital, Kakinada. The participants in this study are the patients who are admitted to the pediatric ward (in patients) with a particular diagnosis and on Antibiotic therapy.

Inclusion criteria:

- A Pediatric patient, aged 5 months to 5 years of either sex, presented with bronchopneumonia.
- Pediatric patients with the diagnosis of bronchopneumonia receive at least one antibiotic.
- Those who are willing to participate the study.

Exclusion criteria:

- Patients who are critically ill.
- Children with ages less than 5 months and more than 5 years.
- Not willing to give consent.

Data Collection and Data Analysis**Data Collection:**

Children of age group 5 months to 5 years were selected. The aim and objectives of the study were explained clearly. Upon their will, data was collected from them using an already prepared data collection form. The collected data was tabulated periodically till the end of the study period. In the end, the data was analyzed statistically to find the age at which bronchopneumonia occurred, the type of Antibiotic therapy used, the Recovery period, and the most widely used drug in children of age group between 5 months to 5 years old.

Data Analysis:

- Data is analyzed qualitatively and quantitatively.

(A)Qualitative:

Data like gender, socioeconomic status, and antibiotics used come under qualitative data.

This qualitative data will be represented using bar diagrams and pie charts.

(B)Quantitative:

Data like age, demographics of patients, and weight come under quantitative data.

This quantitative data will be represented using histograms.

RESULTS

Table 1:

The Age at which bronchopneumonia occurred

Age Group	Frequency	Percentage
< 1 year	30	37.5%
1-2 years	11	13.75%
2-3 years	5	6.25%
3-4 years	10	12.5%
4-5 years	24	30%

Table 2:

Bronchopneumonia occurs in males and females

Age Group	Males	Percentage	Females	Percentage
< 1year	8	10%	22	27.5%
1-2 years	9	11.25%	2	2.5%
2-3 years	1	1.25%	4	5%
3-4 years	4	5%	6	7.5%
4-5 years	12	15%	12	15%
Total	34	42.5%	46	57.5%

Table 3:

Type of Therapy

Type of Therapy	Frequency	Percentage
MONOTHERAPY:		
Amoxiclav	31	38.75%
Cefotaxime	7	8.75%
Ceftriaxone	11	13.75%
Piptaz	1	1.25%
Total	50	62.5%
COMBINATION THERAPY:		
Dual Therapy	21	26.25%
Triple Therapy	6	7.5%
>3 drugs	3	3.75%
Total	30	37.5%

Table 4:

Recovery Period

No of days included as a recovery period	No patients recovered during these days	Percentage
1-4	35	43.7%
4-8	28	35%
8-12	17	21.2%

DISCUSSION

Age-wise distribution of patients affected with bronchopneumonia

Bronchopneumonia has been found to have a higher incidence in younger children in many studies. Similar results were observed in our study where out of 80 subjects 37.5% (30) children experienced bronchopneumonia among the age group less than 1 year, 13.75% (11) children suffered from bronchopneumonia among the age of 1 year to 2 years, 6.25% (5) children experienced bronchopneumonia among the age group of 2years to 3years, 12.5% (10) children experienced bronchopneumonia among the age group of 3years to 4years, 30% (24) children experienced bronchopneumonia among the age group of 4years to 5years.

The results of our study are similar to the following studies

- Wagner CL, Wagstaff P, COXTH, Annibale DJ, J perinatology, Sep 2000, 20(6), 346-50, the study showed that majority of patients were age group of 6 months.
- Nicholas John Bennett Nov5, 2018, study showed that the majority of patients were age group of >5 months.
- Atkison, 2007, the study showed that the majority of patients were age group of ≥ 6 months.

Our study is supported by these authors indicating that bronchopneumonia occurs majorly in patients with age group less than 1 year.

Gender-wise distribution of patients affected with bronchopneumonia

Bronchopneumonia are more common among females than males. The results observed in our study were that out of 80 patients 57.5% (40) were females and 42.5% (34) were males.

The results of our study correlate with the following studies:

- Eduardo Jorge da Fonseca Lima,^{1,2} Maria Julia Gonçalves Mello,^{1,2} Maria de Fátima Pessoa Militão de Albuquerque,³ Maria Isabella Londres Lopes,⁴ George Henrique Cordeiro Serra,² Debora Ellen Pessoa Lima,⁵ and Jailson Barros Correia, study showed that majority of bronchopneumonia affected patients were females than males.

- Lucie Ecker, Theresa J. Ochoa, Martha Vargas, Luis J. Del Valle, Joaquim Ruiz, study showed that majority of bronchopneumonia affected patients were females than males.

Management

Management of bronchopneumonia requires the use of antibiotics. Initially, a single drug is given to treat the above condition and if not successful a combination is given until the required therapeutic outcome is obtained. So based on the number of drugs used a therapy can be monotherapy or a combination therapy.

In our study monotherapy was found to be given in more patients compared to the combination therapy. Monotherapy was given in 62.5% (50) while combination therapy was given in 37.5% (30).

The following articles supported our study:

- Naureen Mushtaq Abdul Sattar Shaikh Khatwani NR Shazia Mohsin, April 2013, vol22, study showed that monotherapy is more effective for treating bronchopneumonia than combination therapy.
- Cristiane Franco Riberio, Giesela Fleisher Ferrari, Jose Roberto Fioretto, 2008, study showed that amoxiclav antibiotic is more effective for treating bronchopneumonia in monotherapy.
- Ziaur Rehman, Zia Ullah, Imod Alishah, vol7 no2 (2017), the study showed that injection ceftriaxone is more effective for treating bronchopneumonia than amoxicillin.
- Svjetlana Loga Zec, Kenan Selmanovic, Natasa Loga Andrijie, Azra Kadic, Lamija Zecevic, Lejila Zunic, 2016; 70(3): 177-181, the study showed that first and third generation of cephalosporins and penicillin antibiotics were mostly used.

Recovery period

Bronchopneumonia are found to be recovered more between 1-4 days 43.7% (35), between 4-8 days 35% (28), and between 8-12 days 21.2% (17).

The following articles supported our study:

- Wagner CL, Wagstaff P, COXTH, annibale DJ, J perinatology, sep 2000, 20(6), 346-50, study showed that recovery period is more during 5.2 days.
- Campbell, 1988, the study showed that the recovery period is more than 7 days.
- Abbate GF, Alagia 1, Gioquinto E, Leonessa V, Caputi M, Guarino C, Miullo E, 1986, study showed that the recovery period is more during 7 days.
- Svjetlana loga Zec, kenan Selmanovic, Natasa Loga Andrije, Azra kadic, Lamija Zecevic, Lejila Zunic, 2016; 70(3): 177-181, study showed that recovery period is more during 3 to 4 days.

However there is slight increase in recovery period of bronchopneumonia, which is slight deviation from the findings of those authors which is not significant considering the variability in the studies.

CONCLUSION

- We found that children of age group less than 1year (37.5%) have high onset of bronchopneumonia. So, we conclude that incidence of bronchopneumonia is maximum during the early stages of life and their frequency decreases with increase in age of the children.
- Bronchopneumonia have been found to be more common among females than males. The results observed in our study where in out of 80 patients 57.5% (40) were females and 42.5% (34) were males. So we conclude that females are more effected than males.
- Monotherapy was found to be given in more patients compared to the combination therapy. Monotherapy was given in 62.5% (50) while a combination therapy is given in 37.5% (30). So we conclude that use of single antibiotic was enough to treat bronchopneumonia in majority of children while the others required the use of two or more drugs for obtaining the required therapeutic outcome.
- Bronchopneumonia are recovered more between 1-4 days 43.7% (35), and between 4-8 days 35% (28), between 8-12 days 21.2% (17). So we conclude that the recovery period in most patients is one to four days.

Overall in our study we found that selecting the single antibiotic is more effective than combination of two or more drugs and recovery period in most of the patients found to be 1-4 days for single antibiotic.

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